
Locative enclitics in Kinyarwanda: A comparative study to Luganda

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Abstract: Languages share the same level of complexity, with simpler areas of grammar being compensated by more complexity elsewhere. Some Bantu languages have some common features in grammar, and these features can make someone think that one language is the same as another. One of the grammatical features that Bantu languages share is Locative enclitics. Locative enclitics are words that cannot stand alone. They need other parts of the world to exist. Kinyarwanda and Luganda share some common features, as they are both Bantu languages. In Kinyarwanda, there are many linguistic features that are also found in Luganda. Some features that are shared include word classes, word morphology, and sentence structure. This paper looks at common linguistic features of Kinyarwanda and Luganda on locative enclitics. This research is descriptive with a qualitative approach. The data used in this study comes from the Kinyarwanda and Luganda grammar books produced by several researchers and institutions in charge of promoting those languages.

Keywords: Bantu language, Kinyarwanda, Locative enclitic, Luganda, Noun class

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1. Introduction

Kinyarwanda and Luganda are both Bantu languages. Kinyarwanda is classified in group J and numbered 61 -J61 by the Tervuren classification of Bantu languages. Luganda is also classified in J group, but coded E15 -JE 15 (Nanteza, 2022; Kawalya, Schryver, Bostoen, 2018; Botne, 1990). This shows that Luganda and Kinyarwanda are closely related languages, as they are spoken in bordering countries. Word categories, sentence construction, and other linguistic features are shared by a big number of Bantu languages. Bantu languages normally obligatorily incorporate object pronouns on the verb (Ssekiryango, 2006). It was also mentioned that the noun class marker is introduced to a verb. The said noun class marker is not only found on a verb, but also on all other modifiers of a noun. This phenomenon is called "Isanisha" in Kinyarwanda (Bizimana, 1998). Sometimes the object is infix (Inyibutsacyuzuzo/indangacyuzuzo/impagike) before the stem of the verb, while others are suffixed after the stem of the verb. The other is the case of locatives in Kinyarwanda and in Luganda.

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Examples:	Kinyarwanda Ku mbabura hari ho umuriro Ku-mbabura-ha-ri= ho u-mu-riro	Luganda Ku sigiri kuliko omuliro Ku- sigiri- ku- li = ko o- mu- liro
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There is fire on the charcoal stove.

Nanteza (2022) argues that locative enclitics are words that cannot stand alone but attach to a verb to make meaning. Their status is ambiguous between a free word and an affix, hence motivating their analysis as enclitics. The enclitics are attached to the post-final position of their hosts. The locative enclitics occur regularly in some Bantu languages (Luganda, Runyankore-Rukiga, Runyoro-Rutooro, Lunda, Ikizu, Fwe, Chichewa, Kinyarwanda, among others). This is also argued by Nsanzabiga and Twilingiyimana (2015) that sometimes personal pronouns can be attached to an infinitive or a conjugated verb, thus: gusom**aho** (to drink on), kurar**ayo** (to pass the night there), kuv**amo** (to come from in), yagiyey**o** (he went there), ntiyakozem**o** (he didn't touch in), mvah**o** (go away from me). What Nanteza (2022) calls "Locative enclitics", is what Zeller and Ngoboka (2005) call "Locative applicative".

2. Locative classes in Kinyarwanda

The Kinyarwanda language has 17 parts of speech (Bizimana, 1998). Among those word categories, Coupez (1980) reveals that some have active affixes that help them to change in their uses (changing words *_amagambo ahinduka*), while others stay as they are because their affixes are not active (non-changing words *_amagambo adahinduka*). For that, Kinyarwanda has two main word classes. Between these two main classes, those with active affixes are also called "morphological words *_amagambo agoragozwa*", including nouns, and those with inactive affixes are called "non-morphological words *_amagambo atagoragozwa*" (Bizimana, 1998; Nsanzabiga & Twilingiyimana, 2015; Kabayiza et al., 2010). Among morphological words, there are adjectives that agree in class and number with the noun they modify.

The Kinyarwanda language has 16 noun classes (*inteko z'amazina*). In Zorc & Nibagwire (2007), Overdulve (1975&1998) states nineteen noun classes, for Kimenyi (1980) is sixteen, while Hands (1952), Hurel (1959), and Cristini (2000) clarify only ten. All noun modifiers agree in 16 noun classes, but for adjectives, three locative classes are added. These are class 17 "ku", class 18 "mu", and class 19 "i". Their corresponding words in the English language are "Prepositions". When we add another locative noun class which is "class 16", locative noun classes become 4, as it is argued by Zeller and Ngoboka (2018) that "...even though Kinyarwanda has four locative noun classes (16, 17, 18 and 19), there is only one locative agreement marker (class 16 ha-), which indiscriminately appears with all locatives, regardless of their noun class".

Examples of 17, 18, and 19 noun class locatives:

Ari ku ishuri 1-be 17ENC 5-school He is at school	Ari mu nzu 1-be 18ENC 16-house He is in the house	Agiye i Kigali 1-go 19ENC 16-Kigali He is going to Kigali
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In the following examples, class 16 (ha) appears with all locatives when we refer to a place which has become a subject of the conjugated verb.

Examples:

I Kigali harashyuha 19 Kigali 16-is hot To Kigali it is hot	Ku rutare harakomera 17 rock 16-is tough At the rock it is tough	Mu nzu harashyuha 18 house 16-is hot It is hot in the house
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This is also argued by Ngoboka (2016) and Zeller & Ngoboka (2018) in their analysis that Kinyarwanda has three secondary locative markers, class 17 (**ku**), class 18 (**mu**) and class 19 (**i**) (reconstructed as Proto-Bantu ***i**- by Meeuussen, 1967). Importantly, however, ... the verb is prefixed with the invariant class 16 subject marker **ha-**. The specific noun class of the preverbal locative subject is thus not reflected in the verbal morphology.

3. Locative classes in Luganda

Nanteza (2022) gives the view of Luganda noun classes in this citation: "*Luganda has 23 noun classes and these are numbered according to the standard Bantu system as 1-23. Nouns are marked for class by a prefix, and noun class agreement is marked on all dependents, including subject marking and object marking. The noun class system in Luganda includes four locative noun classes (16 wa, 17 ku, 18 mu, and 23 e). For all other nouns, a locative can be derived by stacking the locative noun class prefix onto the noun's inherent prefix*".

Examples:

Wano Here	Ku kisenge At the wall	Mu nnyumba In the house	E Makerere At Makerere
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4. Formation of locatives in Kinyarwanda

In Kinyarwanda, locatives are formed from locative noun classes and the addition of the root “ô”, which results in a high-pitched monosyllabic word. In classes 16, 17, and 18, the vowel of the class marker is omitted, while in class 19, the vowel changes to “y”, thus:

16 class: ha+ô becomes hô	18 class: mu+ô becomes mô
17 class: ku+ô becomes kô	19 class: i+ô becomes yô

5. Formative of locative in Luganda

Locative enclitics are derived from locative noun classes, and they attach on any kind of verb (Nanteza, 2022). Luganda has four locative noun classes, thus four locative enclitics. The enclitics in Luganda correspond to the locative noun classes. The enclitics are formed by prefixing an appropriate locative noun class prefix on the enclitic -o. Thus:

e+o: Yo	ku+o: Ko
wa+o: Wo	mu+o: Mo

6. Inversion in locatives

Locative inversion in Bantu languages is a reversed construction whereby the locative phrase is raised to the position of syntactic subject (Guerois, 2017, in Nanteza, 2022). In Kinyarwanda and Luganda, these examples are present.

Examples:

Luganda

E Kampala eriyo amatooke.
E kampala e- ri =yo a- ma- tooke
23 Kampala 23SM- be =23ENC IV- 6- matooke
At Kampala there is matooke.

Kinyarwanda

I Kampala hariyo ibitoki
I Kampala ha-ri=yo i-bi-toki
19 Kampala 16sm-be=19loc i-8-toki
At Kampala there are bananas

In Luganda and Kinyarwanda, locative enclitics are the last after derivational and inflectional suffixes, and they can occur after applicative and other suffixes.

Examples:

Luganda

Obudde bwe nagenderangayo
o- bu- dde bwe- na- gend -er -ang -a =yo
7 time (that) 1sg-past-go-suff=19ENC
The time when I used to go there.
Kimutwalireko
Ki- mu- twal -ir -e =ko
7OM- 1OM- take -APP -SBJV =17ENC
Take it to him/on behalf of him.

Kinyarwanda

Igihe (cyo) najyagayo
I-ki-he (cyo) n-a-gi-aga=yo
14-time when 1sg.SM- go -APP-HAB -FV =23ENC
The time when I used to go there
Kimutwarireyo
Ki-mu-twar-ir-e=yo
7OM-1OM-take-APP-Suff=19ENC
Take it for him/her there

7. Syllable lengthening in Luganda

As Ashton et.al. (1954):423 in Nanteza (2022) say, in Luganda, when locative enclitics are added on a verb, sometimes there is a syllable (vowel) lengthening, and add that “This vowel lengthening occurs in monosyllables and in stems ending in -s- or -z-. Vowel lengthening also occurs in the verb -li- although here it is not regular.”

Examples:

Nvaayo. N- vaa =yo 1sg.SM come.from =23ENC I come from there.	Asazeewo. A- sa -zee =wo 1SM- decide -PERF =16ENC He has decided.	Siibeewo. Si- i- bee =wo NEG- FUT- be =16ENC I will not be there.
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However, in Kinyarwanda, the locative enclitics do not change anything on the verb they are attached to.

8. Main locative class in Kinyarwanda

In Kinyarwanda, the locative noun class (16) marker “ha” is the main marker, which functions as the subject of the verb when there is inversion of the object. But this is not the same case in Luganda, because this language has a big number of noun classes than Kinyarwanda. The difference is remarkable in the following examples:

Luganda

Mu nnyumba eyingidemu abagenyi.
mu- n- nyumba (e)- yingi -dde =mu a- ba- genyi

Kinyarwanda

Mu nzu hinjyemo abashyitsi.
mu-n-zu (ha)-injir-ye=mo a-ba-shyitsi

18 10- house 10SM- enter -PFV =18ENC IV- 2- visitors
In the house the visitors have entered.

18-10-house (16)-enter=18ENC 2-visitors
In the house, the visitors have entered.

Eriyo ebizike (ku luzzi)
E- li =yo e- bi- zike ku luzzi
8SM- be =23ENC IV- 8- gorillas 17 11.well
There are gorillas at the well.

Hariyo ingagi (ku iriba)
ha-ri=yo i-n-gagi ku iriba
16-be=19ENC 9/10-gorillas 17 well
There are gorillas at the well.

Uwizeyimana (2025) calls locative enclitics personal pronoun locatives (Ikinyazina ngenga ndangahantu), and say that some of them can appear as the subject of the verb. Here are examples given:

Ho ndahareba (ahantu)
ho n-ra-ha-reb-a (ahantu)
16ENC 1pers.sing-pres-16Obj Infix-see
There (the place), I see

Mo ntihabona (mu nzu)
Mo nti-ha-bon-a (mu nzu)
18ENC Neg-16Obj Infix-see (in the house)
It is not visible inside (the house)

Yo ndahazi (i Gatsibo)
Yo n-ra-ha-zi
19ENC 1Subj-pres-16Obj Infix-know
(There (at the place “Gatsibo”) I know

Luganda also may have this sentence structure. Kalule (2023) argued this on secret chat.

Wo manyiwo
Wo n-manyi=wo
16ENC 1pers.singular-know=16ENC
There, I know

Mwo nyingidemu
Mu-o n-yingide=mu
18 class-steme 1pers. Singular-enter=16ENC
Inside, I entered

Frequently, Kinyarwanda uses a form of localization that is not the same as the one above. The above example seems to be unwanted repetition; instead, they prefer to use only a verb without the personal pronoun locative.

Examples:

ndahareba (ahantu)
n-ra-ha-reb-a (ahantu)
1pers.sing-pres-16Obj Infix-see
I see the place

ntihabona (mu nzu)
nti-ha-bon-a (mu nzu)
Neg-16Obj Infix-see
It is not visible (in the house)

ndahazi (i Gatsibo)
n-ra-ha-zi
1Subj-pres-16Obj Infix-know
I know (at Gatsibo)

9. The use of locatives

Locatives in Kinyarwanda and Luganda have uses or functions in a sentence. Some may function as politeness markers (especially in Luganda), others may take different functions as Ngoboka (2016) and Nanteza (2022) argue. The locative class, which is commonly known in Kinyarwanda, is class 16 with a locative noun “ahantu” that controls all other locatives, as Ngoboka (2016) says, “Like nouns in other classes, the locative noun *ahaantu* controls concord on the verb, adjectives, and pronouns such as numerals, demonstratives, as well as the associative.”

Examples:

Aha **haantu haawe ndahazi ni heezá ariko harakóonja**.
aha ha-ntu ha-we n-ra-ha-zi ni ha-iizá ariko ha-ra-kóonj-a
16.DEM 16-place 16-2S. 1S-DJ-16.OM-know be 16-nice but 16.SM-DJ-be.cold-FV
This place of yours, I know it, it is nice but cold.

9.1. Expressing a part of something

In Kinyarwanda, the locative, which is delivered from class 16 gives the meaning of a part of something, not the whole.

Examples:

A) Mpa nsomeho
Give I drink+16.Loc
Give me and I drink on

C) Nshaka gutwaraho
I want to drive+16.Loc
I want to drive on

B) Mpa nsome
Give I drink+No Loc
Give me and I drink

D) Nshaka gutwara
I want to drive+No Loc
I want to drive

There is a big semantic difference between A) and B), hence in A) the activity will not continue until the drink is finished. Only a part of the liquid will be drunk. But in B) the liquid may be finished according to someone who is drinking. This

is the same in C), because it is a drive for a short period of time or a short length of the journey, while in D) it is the whole journey.

In examples that Nanteza (2022) gives, there are instances where the enclitics she said are working as politeness markers and function as markers of not the totality of something, but a short while. In the following example, the speaker doesn't want a job of driving, but driving for a short period, but he/she is asking for it politely.

Examples:

Mpaamu nvugemu.
M- wa -a =mu n- vug -e =mu
1sg.OM give -FV =18ENC 1sg.SM- ride -FV =18ENC
Give me I drive for a short while, please.

9.2. Expressing a politeness marker

The locatives sometimes function as politeness markers. At this level, in Luganda, the locatives are working as politeness marker (Nanteza, 2022); however, it is not the same case in Kinyarwanda.

Examples:

1. Nsituliraako ku mugugu guno.
N- situl -ir -aa =ko ku mu- gugu gu- no.
1sg.OM- lift -APP -FV =17ENC 17 3- luggage 3- DEM
Please help me carry this luggage.
2. Maama nnyongeraayo sente.
Maama n- yonger -aa =yo sseente
Mother 1sg.OM- give.more -FV =23ENC 10.money
Mom give me more money please.
3. Mugambe amufunireyo ku nsimbi.
Mu- gamb -e a- mu- fun -ir -e =yo ku n- simbi
1OM- tell -FV 1SM- 1OM- get -APP -FV =23ENC 17LOC 10-money
Tell him to get him some money.
4. Mpaamu nvugemu.
M- wa -a =mu n- vug -e =mu
1sg.OM give -FV =18ENC 1sg.SM- ride -FV =18ENC
Give me I drive for a short while please.

9.3. Two locative enclitics

Nanteza (2022) argues that "...however, and in Luganda, a verb can host two enclitics in the post-final position. (15) indicates two enclitics =mu and =yo hosted on the same verb, although serving different functions. The enclitic =mu, shows time, and the enclitic =yo shows the place. These enclitics are serving different functions on the verb." She adds that: "When two enclitics appear on the verb, only the class 16 and 23 enclitics can appear as locative markers."

Examples:

Obudde bwe nagenderangamuyo.
O-budde bwe na-gend-er-a-nga-mu-yo
IV-14.time when 1sg.SM-root.go-EXT-FV-HAB-18ENC-23LOC
The time when I used to go there.

Nanteza continues that "although it is rare, a verb can permit two enclitics, both serving two different pragmatic functions."

Examples:

Leetakoyyo.	Vvaakowwo.
Leet-a-ko-yyo	Vv-aa-ko-wwo
bring-FV-17ENC-23ENC	leave-FV-17ENC-16ENC
Bring little of that particular one	Leave that particular place (for a little while).

Kinyarwanda cannot support this structure of two locatives on the same verb. When they occur, it brings an ungrammaticality of the verb conjugated, hence the incorrectness of the sentence. Copy and paste from your manuscript.

9.4. Locative with helping verbs

The attachment of the enclitic on either a helping or linking verb results in ungrammaticality if the verb phrase has two verbs (Nanteza, 2022).

Examples:

Yaliko alima mu nnimiro.

Ya- li =ko a- lim -a mu nnimiro

ISM- be- =17ENC 1SM- dig -FV 18LOC 9garden.

Intended: ‘He was digging for some time in the garden.

However, in Kinyarwanda, when a locative of the class 18 is added to a helping verb of the root -ri, there is no place which is located, but the locative serves as an emphaziser of the time being.

Examples:

Urimo urakora iki?

U-ri=mo u-ra-kor-a iki?

2sing be=18Loc 2sing-ra-work what

What are you doing?

Barimo barahinga mu murima.

Ba-ri=mo ba-ra-hing-a mu murima

2-be=18Loc 2-pres-cultivate in the field

They are cultivating in the farm.

Ndimu nshaka akazi.

N-ri=mo n-shak-a akazi

1sing-be=18Loc 1sing-look for a job

I am looking for a job.

9.5. Locative word classes

In Kinyarwanda, there are locative words that are classified into non-changing or non-morphological words. These are called “Imigereke y’ahantu” or “Ingera z’ahantu”. These words show the place where someone or something is located, thus down (hepfo), under (munsi/hasi), on (hejuru), above (haruguru), beside (hirya), and here (hano). With a verb, they are used with a locative class 16.

Examples:

Hepfo hariyo abana.

Hepfo **ha**-ri-yo a-ba-ana

Down 16loc-be=19ENC 2-children

There are children down.

Munsi hari indangasoko.

Munsi **ha**-ri i-n-rangasoko

Under 16loc-be 9/10-references

There are references under.

Hano harashyushye

Hano **ha**-ra-shyushye

Here 16loc-pres-hot

It is hot here.

In Luganda, there are also locative word classes such as “wansi” (down), “wagulu” (above), “eri” and “eno” (beside), “wali” (abroad), “wano” (here).

9.6. Location, which is not summarised

Locative classes are used to introduce a location that is not summarized in one word, as locative words do. Class 18 (mu) and 19 (i) have their corresponding locative enclitics or applicative, notably “mo” for 18 and “yo” for 19. However, on class 17 (ku), there is no corresponding locative enclitic in Kinyarwanda; the enclitic introducing this class is from class 16 “ho”.

Examples:

Mu nzu harimo amatara.

Mu n-zu ha-ri=**mo** a-ma-tara

18loc house 16loc-be=18ENC 6-bulbs

There are bulbs in the house(s).

I Kigali hariyo ubushyuhe.

I Kigali ha-ri=**yo** u-bu-shyuhe
19 loc Kigali 16loc-be=19ENC 14-hotness
There is hotness at Kigali.

Ku ntebe hariho ibitabo
Ku n-tebe ha-ri=**ho** i-bi-tabo
17 loc 9/10-chair 16loc-be=16ENC 8-books
There are books on the chair.

However, in Luganda, all locative classes have their corresponding locative enclitics or applicatives, even “ku” with the locative enclitic “ko”, the difference from Kinyarwanda (Nanteza 2022).

Examples:

Ku ntebe kuliko amagi.
Ku- n- tebe ku- li =17**ko** a- magi
17LOC 9- chair 17SM be =ENC IV- eggs
On the table there are eggs.

Mu nnyumba musingiddemu abagenyi.
Mu n- nyumba mu- yingi- dde =**mu** a- ba- genyi
18LOC 9 house 18SM enter PERF =18ENC IV- 2- visitors
In the house visitors have entered.

E kampala nagenzeeyo ggulo.
e- Kampala na- genz- ee =**yo** ggulo
23LOC Kampala 1sg.SM- go PST =23ENC yesterday
At Kampala I went there yesterday.

There is another difference in localization between Kinyarwanda and Luganda. There is an introduction on locative classes, notably class 17 “ku” and 18 “mu” on a conjugated verb in Luganda, contrary to Kinyarwanda, where the verb is introduced by the locative class 16 “ha”.

Examples:

Luganda

Ku ntebe kuliko amagi.
Ku- n- tebe ku- li =17**ko** a- magi
17LOC 9- chair 17SM be =ENC IV- eggs
On the table there are eggs.

Mu nnyumba musingiddemu abagenyi.
Mu n- nyumba mu- yingi- dde =**mu** a- ba- genyi
18LOC 9 house 18SM enter PERF =18ENC IV- 2- visitors
In the house visitors have entered.

Kinyarwanda

Ku meza hariho amagi
Ku-meza 16lo**cha**-ri=ho a-ma-gi
17loc 6-table 16loc-be=16ENC 6-eggs
There are eggs on the table

Mu nzu hinjyemo abashyitsi
Mu n-zu 16lo**cha**-injyemo a-ba-shyitsi
18loc 9 house 16loc-enter=18ENC 2-visitors
Visitors have entered in the house

In Kinyarwanda, locative enclitics “mo” and “yo” can replace a place in a sentence. On the side, in Luganda, it is the locative enclitic “yo”. Nanteza (2022) states that a locative enclitic, however, does not need to replace a noun phrase (NP) mentioned earlier (overtly) in the discussion. It may point to something that is absent from the discourse, but which is clearly understood by the discourse participants, or in context. ...the locative enclitic =yo indicates the location (‘there’, i.e. at the place ... is) of the event referred to.

Examples:

Omwana asobola okufumbirayo emmere.
O- mu- ana a- sobol -a o- ku- fumb -ir -a =yo e- n- mere
IV- 1- child 1SM- can -FV IV- INF- cook -APPL -FV =23ENC IV- 9- food
The child can cook food from there (at the place where the child is).

Umwana ashobora gutekeraayo ibiryo
u-mu-ana a-shobor-a ku-tek-ir-a=**yo** i-bi-ri-o
1-child 1-can-fv 15-inf-cook-appl=19ENC 8-food
The child can cook food from there (at the place where the child is)

Umwana ashobora kubeneramo ibibazo
u-mu-ana a-shobor-a ku-bon-ir-a=**mo** i-bi-bazo

1-child 1-can-fv 15-inf-find-appl=18ENC 8-promblems

The child can find/get problems from inside there (in the place where the child is)

The locative enclitic “ko” is commonly used in the Luganda language, but not in Kinyarwanda. This is to emphasize the difference between these two languages. In Kinyarwanda, it seems that, there is no locative enclitic of this type, but the locative class is there (17), but the corresponding locative enclitics seems to be absent.

Examples:

Kimutwalireko.

Ki- mu- twal -ir -e =ko

7OM- 1OM- take -APP -SBJV =17ENC

Take it to him/on behalf of him.

Nsituliraako ku mugugu guno.

N- situl -ir -aa =ko ku mu- gugu gu- no.

1sg.OM- lift -APP -FV =17ENC 17 3- luggage 3- DEM

Please help me to carry this luggage.

Yanguwako omusaja tatusaanga.

Ya- guw -a =ko o- mu- sajja ta- tu- saang -a.

1SM- hurry -FV =17ENC IV- 1- man NEG- 2pl.OM- find -FV

Hurry, let's the man finds us.

9.7. Urgent marking

In Luganda, enclitics can be used as urgent markers. This is confirmed by Nanteza (2022), saying that the enclitic also brings out the idea of “urgency” when added to a verb. One speaker consulted said that whenever she wants to show that something has to be done urgently, she adds an enclitic to the verb.

Examples:

Genderawo.

gend -er -a =wo

go -APP -FV =16ENC

Go right away.

Ekitabo kireeterewo kati.

E- ki- tabo ki- leet -er -e =wo kati

IV- 7- book 7OM- bring -APP -FV =16ENC now

Bring the book right now.

Yanguwako omusaja tatusaanga.

Ya- guw -a =ko o- mu- sajja ta- tu- saang -a.

1SM- hurry -FV =17ENC IV- 1- man NEG- 2pl.OM- find -FV

Hurry, lest the man finds us.

Nanteza (2022) also argues that, a speaker can sometimes choose to use other words that mean urgency together with the enclitic. The following is the example where the speaker adds the adverb *kati* (now) to imply urgency:

Examples:

Nkugambye kitwalirewo kati.

n- ku- gamb -ye ki- twal -ir -e =wo kati

1sg.SM- 2sg.OM- tell -PERF 7OM- take -APP -FV =16ENC now

I have told you to take it right now.

9.8. Expressing for a short period

In Kinyarwanda, the enclitic “ho” may show the idea of a short period of time or in a short moment.

Examples:

Nsunikiraho

ny-suniki-ir-a=ho

1pers sing Obj-push-appl=16ENC

Push for me (for a short period)"/ “Help me to push a bit.

Mfashaho nihagarike

ny-fash-a=ho n-ihagarik-e

1pers sing Obj-take for=16ENC 1pers Subj-urinate
Take for me (for a short period of time) then I go for a short call.

This is also found in Luganda, as the minimizing function of the enclitics. The minimizing function is also carried on in the time aspect, where the enclitic means for a short period of time (Nanteza, 2022).

Examples:

Tugendeyokko.

Tu- gend -e =yo =kko

1pl.SM- go -FV =23ENC =17ENC

Let us go there for a short while.

In Luganda, Nanteza (2022) argues, the partitive function of the locative enclitics goes hand in hand with a “minimizing” function. The minimizing function, i.e. just a little bit is expressed by both =ko and =mu as (A)-(C) show:

- A) Nensituka nentagalamu.
Ne- n- situk -a ne n- tagal -a =mu.
And 1sg.SM- get.up -FV and 1sg.SM- sway -FV =18ENC
And I got up and I swayed a little bit.
- B) Naye toswalako?
Naye te- o- swal -a =ko?
But NEG- 2sg.SM- shame -FV =17ENC
But do you feel a little bit of shame?
- C) Atambulako.
A- tambul -a =ko
1SM- walk -FV =17ENC
He walks a little bit.

9.9. Something is usual

In Kinyarwanda, the enclitic “ho” of class 16 is sometimes used with the verb “kureba (to see)”, to show that something is done easily, or to say that a person is more talented/gifted/quick, famous or notorious in what the infinitive or noun phrase that introduces the sentence means.

Examples:

Kwigisha arebaho.

Kwigisha a-reb-a=**ho**

To teach (inf) 1 Subj-see=16ENC

He is gifted in teaching.

Ku nkumi arebaho

Ku n-kumi a-reb-a=**ho**

17loc 10-girls 1 Subj-see=16ENC

He is notorious in dating young girls.

Kwamamaza arebaho

Kwamamaza a-reb-a=**ho**

Kwamamaza (inf) 1 Subj-see-a=16ENC

He/she is gifted in advertising.

Mu izamu arebaho

Mu i-zamu a-reb-a=**ho**

18loc 5-goal 1 Subj-see=16ENC

He is a famous/ celebrated goalkeeper.

9.10. Other functions of locatives

Apart from the above-mentioned functions of locatives, there are others that are not popular. These include expressing a doubt, concern, and/or similar.

9.11. Doubt

In Luganda, the presence of the enclitic “ko” on the verb (in B) signals doubt. The speaker is not certain of the mother’s answer or knowledge of what is being talked about. Here, the absence of the enclitic “ko” (in A) indicates the absence of doubt, for example, that the speaker is certain that the mother knows the right answer (Nanteza, 2022).

A) mubuuze Peter.

mu- buuz -e Peter

1OM- ask -SBJ Peter

Ask Peter.

B) mubuuzeeko Peter.

Mu- buuz -e -e =ko Peter

1OM- ask -SBJ =17ENC Peter

Ask Peter.

9.12. Instead of

The enclitic, in Luganda, may bring the meaning of “Instead of”. The idea of “instead of” and “surprise” is established when the enclitic =mu is attached on different verbs. When the enclitic is attached, it adds a nuance of surprise to the

sentence and implies that the action is not supposed to be done in a particular way. This function is only of the enclitic “mu”, not of other enclitics (Nanteza, 2022).

Examples:

Abaana baguzeemu ffene.
A- ba- ana ba- guz- ee =*mu* ffene
IV- 2- child 2SM- buy -PERF =18ENC 14.irish.potatoes
The children have instead bought jackfruit.

Aleseemu mugaati!
A- le -see =*mu* mu- gaati!
1SM- bring -PERF =18ENC 3- bread
He has brought bread instead.

Natunzeemu ziri enzirugavu.
Na- tun -zee =*mu* zi- ri e- n- zi- rugavu
1sg.SM- sold -PERF =18ENC 10- DEM IV- 10- 10- black
I sold the other black ones instead.

9.13. Concern

Nanteza (2022) states that when =*ko* is attached to the verbs *okwogera* “to talk” and *okukwata* “to touch”, the ideas of “concern” and “about” are shown.

Examples:

Weeyogereko nga bulijjo.
Wee- yog -er -e =*ko* nga bulijjo
RFM talk -APP -FV =17ENC HAB usually
Talk about yourself as usual.

Wabula kyankutteko nnyo.
Wabula ki- a- n- kutt -e =*ko* nnyo
By.the.way 7SM- PST- 1OM- touch -FV =17ENC much
By the way, I felt really concerned.

9.14. Like that

In Kinyarwanda, the enclitic “ko” may have the meaning of “like that” or “with what you have” as in (A) and (B), when attached to a verb. However, when it is separated from a verb, it serves as a conjunction like in (C) and (D).

- A) Naje naniwe ndyamirako.
n-a-z-ye n-naniwe n-ryam-ir-a=*ko*
1sub-past-come-appl 1sub-tired 1sub-sleep-appl=17ENC
I came very tired, and I slept with tiredness.
- B) Yagiye kuvoma agenderako.
a-a-gi-ye ku-vom-a a-gend-ir-a=*ko*
1sub-past-go-appl to fetch 1sub-go-appl=17ENC
She went to fetch water and went (disappeared) like that.
- C) Twavuga ko bazatsinda ibizamini.
Tu-a-vug-aga =*ko* ba-za-tsind-a i-ki-zamini
1sub.plur-past-say-appl 17ENC 2sub-fut-succeed-appl 7-exam
We have been saying that they will succeed in the exam.
- D) Ntiwumva ko uzanye igitekerezo kiza!
Nti-u-umv-a =*ko* u-z-an-ye i-ki-tekerezo ki-iza!
Neg-2sub-hear-appl =17ENC 2sub-come-appl 7-idea 7-good!
Don't you hear that you bring a good idea!

10. Enclitics with the Adjective of quality

The enclitics serve a comparative function when added onto adjectives in Luganda. In this case, the enclitic is still attached to the post-final position of the adjective, and a comparison is then made. For the comparative function, only the class 17 enclitic =*ko* and class 23 =*yo* are used (Nanteza, 2022).

In the examples given, (A) refers to the shop attendant who is told to choose the most beautiful dress and give it to the customer among all the dresses in the shop. In (B), a girl was being sent for a basket to be used in packing the gifts

to take to the in-laws. She is sent for a basket, but brings a small one, hence being sent to bring the one bigger than the one she had brought:

- A) Leeta ekisingayo obulungi.
Leet -a e- ki- sing -a =yo o- bu- lungi
bring -FV IV- 7- most -FV =23ENC IV- 14- beautiful
Bring the most beautiful one.
- B) Muwe ekineneko ku kino.
Mu- w -e e- ki- nene =ko ku ki- no
IOM- give -FV IV- 7- big =17ENC 17 7- DEM
Give her one that is bigger than this one.

This is the same case to Kinyarwanda, when the enclitic is added to an adjective of quality, sometimes this last becomes an adjectival noun or it stays as it is, and only enclitics “ho” and “mo” can take the comparative function, which is “a bit less or more than”. At this time, there is a space between an adjective and a locative enclitic.

Examples:

Nzanira ikinini ho (gato).
Ny-z-an-ir-a i-ki-nini =ho (gato)
Iobj-come-appl aug-7-big =16ENC (a bit)
Bring me the big a bit.

Zana ikintu kinini ho (gato).
z-an-a i-ki-ntu ki-nini =ho (gato)
come-appl aug-7-big =16ENC (a bit)
Bring me something bigeer a bit.

Yarongoye umwiza ho (gato)
a-a-rongor-ye u-mu-iza =ho (gato)
Isub-past-marry-appl aug-1-beautiful =16ENC (a bit)
He has married the beautiful one a bit.

Yarongoye umukobwa mwiza ho (gato)
a-a-rongor-ye u-mu-kobwa mu-iza =ho (gato)
Isub-past-marry-appl aug-1-girl 1-beautiful =16ENC (a bit)
He has married a beautiful girl a bit

Iriya nka ni nziza mo (gake)
i-riya n-ka ni n-ziza =mo (gake)
9-that 9-cow is 9-good =18ENC (a bit)
That cow is a bit better.

Iriya ni inziza mo (gake).
i-riya ni i-n-ziza =mo (gake)
9-that is 9-good =18ENC (a bit)
That is a bit better.

Ashobora kuba ari mubi mo (cyane)
a-shobor-a ku-ba a-ri mu-bi =mo (cyane)
Isubj-can-appl to be Isubj-be 1-bad =18ENC (a bit more)
She may be a bit worse.

Ndabona ari umubi mo (gahoro).
n-ra-bon-a a-ri u-mu-bi =mo (gahoro)
Isubj-can-appl to be Isubj-be aug-1-bad =18ENC (a bit more)
She may be the worst a bit.

11. Conclusion

This paper focused on showing the similarities of the uses of locative enclitics in Kinyarwanda and Luganda. There are some differences when Luganda has got many functions of enclitics than Kinyarwanda. All enclitics in Luganda such as “wo”, “ko”, “mu/mo” and “yo” are frequently used; however, in Kinyarwanda, only three enclitics are commonly used, such as “ho”, “mo”, and “yo”. The other enclitic “ko” in Kinyarwanda is used rarely, and as it is attached on a verb, it wants to mean “with what you have” or like that”. When it is not attached to a verb, it serves as a conjunction, what other enclitics in the same language cannot do.

It was also mentioned that Kinyarwanda enclitics can take the comparative function. At this time, they are separated from the adjectives of quality or the adjectival noun they want to compare. These enclitics are not four as they are in Kinyarwanda, but two, which are “ho” and “mo”.

In Luganda, enclitics have different functions. These are locative functions and non-locative functions which are comparative function, partitiveness function, concern and about function, instead of function, marker of uncertainty, urgency marker, and politeness marker.

In Kinyarwanda, locative enclitics do not function as politeness markers, because politeness in Kinyarwanda is marked another way. However, all other functions can be taken.

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